

REAL-TIME ROBUST DETECTION OF MOVING OBJECTS IN CLUTTERED SCENES

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ABSTRACT

Object recognition is a very important task in computer vision and different techniques have been presented to solve it. In this paper a Hough-type low-computational algorithm for detection of objects in cluttered scenes is presented. The approach is based on the detection of the shape of an object, modeled by means of a set of corners. An automatically model learning method is introduced. The method is used in an existing video-surveillance system in order to increase its detection performances. Results show that the proposed approach provides good performances with low processing times.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to the increasing demand of complex vision systems based on scene interpretation, detection and tracking of moving objects from image sequences is becoming a more and more important task. In real applications, moving objects present high complexity and they must be detected in real time with low-cost architectures. Existing object detection algorithms decrease their performances when scene complexity raises up as evaluated in [1]. For this reasons it is necessary to introduce simple and fast algorithms that use robust features in order to detect complex objects in real time with good performances. In this paper a real-time robust algorithm for the detection of moving objects in cluttered scenes is presented. The approach is based on a preliminary extraction step concerning the shape of the object. In literature there are many methods for describing the shape of an object. (e.g. lines [2], snakes [3], Generalized Hough Transform (GHT) [4] etc). The above methods present medium and high processing times and work well for structured man-made objects. However some methods are not so efficient for natural non-rigid objects such as persons. In our case we consider an existing High Level Image Processing (HLIP) system for video-surveillance (VS) applications described in [5] aiming at detecting, localizing and tracking moving objects in a complex, highly cluttered scene. The low-level image processing of this system focuses attention in regions where a change is detected with reference to a back-

ground image. This technique can provide an accurate position for single objects when they are isolated, but cannot calculate the position of objects when they are merged in the image plane.

In this paper a shape detection algorithm is introduced that is based upon a model of the object created from a set of corners detected in the image plane. The algorithm is applied to the existing video-surveillance system in order to detect the single objects within the group of joined objects.

The paper is structured as follows: section 2 describes the proposed method, section 3 presents an overview of an existing VS system used to test the proposed approach. Section 4 presents the results obtained and finally section 5 draws conclusions.

2 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The considered AVS system would cope with a wider set of applications if it would be provided with the possibility of detecting single objects within pre-selected regions of interest. Such goal can be achieved by extracting a shape model from the single regions of interest and successively applying it to the resulting merged region in order to separate the original object shapes.

The presented approach to object detection is a variation of the Generalized Hough Transform (GHT). The GHT is a technique used to find arbitrary curves in an image without having a parametric equation of them. A look-up table called R-table is used to model the template shape of the object. This R-table is used as a transform mechanism.

To build the R-Table first a reference point and several feature points of the shape are selected. For each feature point the orientation α of the tangential line at that point, the length r , and the orientation θ of the radial vector that joins the reference point and the feature point can be calculated. If n is the number of feature points, a $2 \times n$ indexed table can be created using all n pairs (r, θ) and using α as index. This table is the model of the shape and it can be used with a transformation to find occurrences of the same object in other images. The shape is localized by using a voting technique. The

Figure 1: Corner GHT variation.

edges of the image are extracted, and for every point the orientation α is computed. Using α as an index for the R-table, the pair (r, θ) is extracted. Using the pair (r, θ) , the possible position for the reference point can be computed and an accumulator of its position is incremented. Although some points that do not belong to the desired shape will have similar α and will introduce false reference points, the maximum accumulator value will occur with high probability at the actual reference point.

In our approach, a variation computationally simpler than the GHT is used in order to automatically extract the model of the object (R-table) and also to individuate the position of the object (voting). Corners extracted from the object are used as feature points and a different parametrization is used. Instead of using pairs (r, θ) , pairs (dx, dy) are used (dx and dy are the differences in x and y with respect to the reference point). The second variation is used just to speed up the processing calculations. Instead of using a $2 \times n$ indexed table, a $3 \times n$ table is used. The first value is the angle direction ω of the gradient vector at the corner position with respect to the original image. The obtained triplet (ω, dx, dy) is used to model the position and orientation of the corner with respect to the reference point. In this approach, for a corner, not all of the n possible corners are voted, but only the ones that have ω similar to the one obtained, thus minimizing computational time and memory requirements.

The presented GHT variation is shown in figure 1.

2.1 Corner Extraction

A simple and fast algorithm for corner extraction is used. First the gradient of the input gray level image is computed using the *Sobel* operator [6]. Edges are extracted by using the gradient magnitude: a pixel of the image is considered to be a point of an edge if its gradient magnitude is greater than a fixed threshold.

If a large variation in the direction of the gradient is found in a neighborhood of edge points, then a corner is

Figure 2: Corner extraction images: (a) original (b) edges (c) corners.

Figure 3: Extracted corners for 3 consecutive frames.

detected. The algorithm for corner extraction evaluates the maximum variation of gradient direction of the edges points inside a square kernel. If the maximum variation is greater than a threshold then the pixel at the center of the kernel is selected as a corner and its gradient direction is fixed as the corner direction.

Figure 2 shows the corner extraction steps: a) original image, b) edges image, and c) corners extracted.

A group of corners extracted in this way can be considered as a set of features in order to represent an object in the proposed method characterized by a good level of robustness in presence of small changes in shape. However, a further step is necessary to make more robust the obtained shape descriptor. As shown in figure 3, several consistent corners are extracted in consecutive frames of a sequence for the same object.

The approach for object detection is divided in two phases: Model learning (generation of R-Table) and Object detection (voting).

2.2 Model Learning

The input to the learning model system shown in Figure 4 is the gray level image of the desired object. The center of the gray-level image is selected as reference point. The gradient operator is applied to the image in order to extract edges and for every edge point the direction of the gradient is calculated. Then the filter for extraction of corners is applied. The direction of the corner α

Figure 4: Model learning block diagram.

Figure 5: Object detection block diagram.

is the gradient direction in its position. For each corner dx and dy can be calculated by evaluating the difference between the reference point and the position of the corner. These values are then stored in the R-table that represents the obtained model of the object..

If possible, for obtaining a more robust model, the previous method is applied to different images of the object (i.e. frames of a sequence). Then a unique R-table is constructed by selecting the corners that are present in most of the images at the same location and with the same orientation (consistent ones) allowing small variations in their values.

2.3 Object Detection

The inputs to the system are the R-table of the searched object and the gray level image in which the object should be present. As in the learning model phase, the gradient operator and the filter for corner extraction are applied (see Figure 5). For every extracted corner, α is computed and if present in the R-table, then the possible position for the reference point can be calculated using (dx, dy) and its accumulator can be incremented. As in the GHT, the reference point will be found at the maximum accumulator value.

3 VIDEO-SURVEILLANCE SYSTEM

The proposed approach is applied to a previous existing video-surveillance system described in [5]. The system uses the outputs from the detection of moving objects in [5], which mainly detects bounding rectangles of the objects in the scene and graphs of correspondences between them.

In particular, each detected moving area in the scene is bounded by a rectangle to which a numerical label is assigned. Thanks to the detection of the temporal correspondences among bounding boxes, a graph-based temporal representation of the dynamics of the image primitives can be built as detected by specific image segmentation modules at each instant. In particular, in figure 6a we can see three bounding boxes labeled by numbers 1,2 and 3: the boxes correspond to the extreme left nodes of the graph in figure 6b. Connections between nodes in the graph represent temporal correspondences between blobs.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: (a) bounding boxes, (b) temporal graph representing correspondences between bounding boxes.

This temporal graph provides information on the current bounding boxes and their relations to the boxes detected in the previous frames. An isolated box has the same label as in the previous frame. If the current rectangle is a union of some boxes of the previous frame, the label assigned to it will be a new number and the information of the originating rectangles is known.

This system cannot separate objects inside merged rectangles. The proposed approach aims at applying the method described in section 2 to the output of this system using the rectangles and the correspondences graphs in order to detect the objects present in isolated boxes when they merge so forming a group.

The initial hypothesis is that the object will be at least partially visible after the union with the group.

The procedure is to apply the learning model phase to the isolated rectangles in 2 or 3 frames before the union takes place. When the boxes are merged, the object detection phase is used in order to find the position of the objects inside the merged rectangles.

4 RESULTS

The proposed approach based on model learning and object detection using corners has been tested by a set of sequences (10 sequences) each during from 1.5 to 3 minutes; a sample of such tests is presented in figure 7.

The threshold used where $th = 10$ for gradient magnitude and $\Delta\theta = 30$ degrees for angle variation. The number of corners extracted vary from 25 to 70 corners per object.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 7: Method results: (a) and (c) learning frames, (b) and (d) detection of objects.

The bounding boxes are the output of the video-surveillance system described in section 3. The cross identifies the reference point of the object and the label of the object in the previous frames.

For the evaluated sequences we obtained a percent of correct detection of 90% and a false alarm rate of 20% (in some images more than one maximum points were found).

The processing time for the model learning phase and the object detection depends on the complexity of the objects to be computed, although the average time is about 350 ms. This results allow real-time applications.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Results show that the proposed approach provides good performances with low processing times, regarding such method as a very good solution for the object detection in cluttered scenes.

A real-time robust algorithm for object detection in cluttered scenes has been presented, which allows performances with low processing times. Corners of the objects are used as feature points for modeling the shape of the object. The algorithm is based in two phases, a model learning phase and a tracking phase.

Presented results show the validity of such method for real applications.

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